

“Merging Search Engine Needs”

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Abstract

The two previous meetings of the Open Search Foundation demonstrated the diversity in interpretation of the term “search engine”. Developers and users have –over time– developed a broad interpretation of that term, which leads to confusion.

In this short talk, I want to address some fundamental differences between the projects of some speakers. Where do their projects differ and where do they have overlapping needs? This introduces an alternative infra-structure which has practical advantages.

Presentations

Without an attempt to be complete, let’s recall some of the presentations during both meetings to collect some crucial characteristics.

OSF Chair Dr Stefan Voigt has a vision of a “Google alternative”: a privacy aware search engine, which is offering people a way to avoid existing options which each are commercial and/or politically confined. This new European platform should offer a “Linux kernel”-like cooperation model, so everyone can use the collected data and help to improve accessing it. The system should enable research in search technologies and help other studies.

Building such infrastructure requires a continuous scanning of websites, huge storage, and a smart result ranking system. Storing the collected data has GDPR complications, copyright violation issues. The index is updated slowly.

In a second talk during the first OSF meeting, Mr Marco Verile presented EMM: the European Media Monitor. The application scans media websites to classify articles which are found on those pages.

The articles are not stored and not distributed, which saves many juridical pitfalls. It’s application has other challenges: scans must happen often (more than

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once an hour), media pose license restrictions, and often require manual registration and payment. They do not fit in a freely shared index.

The third example I pick was presented during the second meeting. Suggested was to include some of the fast datasets of CERN in the search index. Since the ‘go-pher’ network was released back in 1991, we know that it is rather inconvenient to hop from server to server to find the data you are looking for. Merging indices into one will improve that.

On the other hand: CERN data is of super high quality, which allows very precise searches. Web texts are extremely chaotic, and of poor quality and consistence: generic text search engines return sloppy results. Merging these two characteristics will certainly result in poorer results than keeping them apart.

Policies

Two proposed structures for an initial Search Engine set-up show the predictable flow:

1. a *crawler* fetches pages;
2. text of the pages get *indexed*; and
3. index get search by *apps* (for instance an user interface)

Apps may also add information back into the index. Other external sources, like CERN may contribute their information to be found. Various collections in the index will get their specific interfaces.

Maintaining information is hard. For example, you will get into licensing, juridical, performance, timeliness, financial, anti-spam, and copyright problems; to name just a few. Let alone creating and maintaining hundreds of interfaces for a “data lake”. This will pose restrictions on the collection, which will needlessly limit the applications.

As example: the Dutch National Library (KB) collects the history of 13,000 websites, mainly containing political and social content. It has a signed contract with each website. You can only watch the pages when you are physically in their building. Only that way, they can fulfill the requirements of the GDPR.

This is not too far away from EMM: their application has contracts with media to be able to scan them. Some media are even trickier: Twitter information can be scanned without license *unless* you are a governmental organization. In that case, written permission is needed to each organization, and the end-user must show itself to Twitter so scan results cannot be shared.

Conclusion

Whether we like it or not, any *index* between the source data (on web-sites) and application (for research or search) will put bounds on how and what the application is able to do. This can only go two ways: either create an omniscient super-index which no-one has ever been able to do before, or fragment the infrastructure into reusable building bricks which applications themselves glue together.

One brick might be an index for text search. Another brick may do language detection for websites. One splits web-pages into news-items. Another one renders web-pages. A brick to translate PDF into text. A researcher with too much disk-space produces an alternative index with a different ranking algorithm.

Building a “Google”-like search index is only a special case of needs which other people have presented during the first two OSF meetings. A cluster of flexible mesh/(micro-)services based on data streams (feeds) can benefit all. How this can be achieved architecturally is the content of a second talk.

About the Author

Mark Overmeer got his Master in Computing Science from the Radboud University in Nijmegen, The Netherlands in 1990. The title of his thesis was “Real-time fault-tolerance in Multi-Controller systems”, which shows his early love for very complex networks.

After University, he worked as system programmer in the super-computer environment of the NLR, the Royal Netherland Aerospace Centre. He implemented distributed user accounting and backup networks at the time no commercial products were available yet.

After six years at NLR, he worked as UNIX trainer –programming and system administration for professionals– until his side-projects grew too large to be combined with a full-time contract job.

Since 2002, Mark worked as self-employed programmer for many different smaller and larger companies. In the past years (among other projects) full-time for the NCSC: the National Cyber Security Center of the Dutch Ministry of Justice, as developer/maintainer of the website monitoring system Taranis.

His side-track activities have resulted in many different products. For example: a huge satellite image archive (two clusters with each six servers packed with disks), over 70 libraries for the Perl programming language (mainly XML and email related), and over 100 presentations at (mainly Open Source) conferences.

The development of the 10th website in the Netherlands in 1994 triggered his interest for search engines. This led to two papers about that subject contributed for a TERENA-NORDUnet Networking Conference in 1999. The papers were publish

in IEEE Computer Networking.¹² Mark has made a few attempts to interest people to seriously improve Search Engines since, and recently gave that more focus.

Mark is closely involved with the NLUUG (Dutch Unix User Group), the Dutch Perl Foundation, the university's Computing Science Alumni group, and the CAC-ert certificate authority. He also has some long-term relation with the NLnet Foundation.

¹“A Search Interface for my Questions”, IEEE 31(1999)2263-2270

²“My Personal Search-Engine”, IEEE 31(1999)2271-2279